

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Paper

Formulation and Evaluation of a Polyherbal Anti-Inflammatory Functional Candy Containing Boswellia, Cinnamon, and Clove Extract for Joint Support

Neha Chaudhari*, Sandeep Mukati, Nivesh Pratap Singh Gurjar, Sudha Vengurlekar

University Institute of Pharmacy, Oriental University, Indore, (M.P.), India.

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 12 May 2026

Keywords:

Polyherbal candy, Anti-inflammatory, Boswelliaserrata, Cinnamomumverum, Joint support, Syzygiumaromaticum, Herbal formulation

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.20136268

ABSTRACT

The present and were evaluated for organoleptic properties, physicochemical parameters, weight variation, hardness, pH, friability, microbial limit test, and stability studies. Among all formulations, formulation F5 was identified as the optimized formulation based on its The present study aimed to formulate and evaluate a polyherbal anti-inflammatory functional candy containing Boswelliaserrata, Cinnamomumverum(cinnamon), and Syzygiumaromaticum (clove) for joint support. These medicinal plants are well known for their anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and analgesic properties, attributed to bioactive constituents such as boswellic acids, cinnamaldehyde, and eugenol. A total of nine formulations (F1–F9) were prepared by varying the concentrations of herbal extractssuperior taste, texture, uniformity, and stability. The optimized formulation exhibited acceptable physicochemical characteristics, good mechanical strength, and compliance with microbial safety standards. Stability studies confirmed that the formulation remained stable under specified conditions without significant changes. The synergistic effect of the selected herbal ingredients may enhance anti-inflammatory activity and support joint health. The candy dosage form offers improved palatability, ease of administration, and better patient compliance compared to conventional dosage forms. In conclusion, the developed polyherbal functional candy represents a promising, safe, and patient-friendly nutraceutical approach for inflammation management and joint support; however, further in vivo and clinical studies are required to validate its therapeutic efficacy and long-term safety.

***Corresponding Author:** Neha Chaudhari

Address: University Institute of Pharmacy, Oriental University, Indore, (M.P.), India

Email ✉: nehachaudhari6396@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

INTRODUCTION

Inflammation is a complex biological response of body tissues to harmful stimuli such as pathogens, damaged cells, or irritants, and plays a central role in the pathogenesis of various chronic conditions, including arthritis and joint disorders. Persistent inflammation contributes to pain, stiffness, and reduced mobility, significantly affecting quality of life. Although conventional anti-inflammatory drugs provide symptomatic relief, their long-term use is often associated with adverse effects, prompting the need for safer and more sustainable alternatives. Herbal medicine has gained increasing attention as a promising approach for managing inflammatory conditions due to its perceived safety, efficacy, and holistic action. Among various medicinal plants, *Boswelliaserrata*, *Cinnamomumverum* (cinnamon), and *Syzygiumaromaticum* (clove) are well-known for their potent anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and analgesic properties. *Boswelliaserrata* contains boswellic acids that inhibit inflammatory mediators, while cinnamon exhibits immunomodulatory and antioxidant effects. Clove, rich in eugenol, contributes to both anti-inflammatory and analgesic activities. The synergistic combination of these herbal extracts may enhance therapeutic efficacy and provide a natural alternative for joint support. The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a polyherbal anti-inflammatory functional In recent years, there has been a growing interest in functional confectionery products that not only offer palatability but also deliver health benefits. Functional candies represent an innovative and patient-friendly dosage form, particularly for individuals who prefer non-conventional oral formulations. They improve compliance, especially among pediatric and geriatric populations, and can serve as an effective medium for delivering herbal bioactives. candy

incorporating extracts of *Boswelliaserrata*, cinnamon, and clove. The formulated candies were subjected to various physicochemical and organoleptic evaluations, including color, consistency, surface characteristics, odour, pH, and stability studies. The objective of this research is to develop a stable, effective, and palatable herbal formulation that can provide supportive care in managing joint inflammation while ensuring safety and consumer acceptability.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Dried extracts of *Boswelliaserrata*, *Cinnamomumverum* (cinnamon), and *Syzygiumaromaticum* (clove) were procured from a certified herbal supplier. Sucrose, glucose syrup, citric acid, and purified water were used as base ingredients for candy preparation. All reagents and chemicals used were of analytical grade.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Extraction Methods of herbal drugs

Clove oil was extracted from dried flower buds of *Syzygiumaromaticum* by the steam distillation method. The coarsely powdered clove buds were placed in a distillation flask, and steam was passed through the plant material to vaporize the volatile oil. The vapors containing essential oil and water were then condensed using a condenser, and the distillate was collected. The clove oil was separated from the aqueous layer using a separating funnel and stored in an airtight container at a cool temperature until further use. The extracts of *Cinnamomumverum* (bark) and *Boswelliaserrata* (resin) were prepared by the maceration method. The dried plant materials were coarsely powdered and soaked separately in a suitable solvent (such as hydroalcoholic solution or distilled water) in a closed container for 48–72 hours with occasional stirring. After maceration,

the mixtures were filtered using muslin cloth followed by filter paper. The filtrates were concentrated using a water bath at controlled temperature (below 50–60°C) to obtain semi-solid extracts. These extracts were then stored in airtight containers under cool and dry conditions for further formulation use.

2.2.2 Preparations of Polyherbal Candy

- A) Sucrose and glucose syrup were accurately weighed and dissolved in purified water.
- B) The solution was heated with continuous stirring until a clear syrup was formed.
- C) The mixture was further heated to 140–150°C (hard crack stage).
- D) Citric acid was added to improve taste and stability.
- E) The syrup was allowed to cool to 80–90°C.
- F) Polyherbal extract (Boswelliaserrata, Cinnamomumverum) and clove oil were added.

Fig. 1: Preparations of Polyherbal Candy

Table 1: Formulation table for composition of Polyherbal Candy

Drug	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Syzygiumaromaticum(Clove)ml	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3
Cinnamon Verum (Dalchini) gm	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	3
BoswillaSerrata(SalaiGuggul) gm	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Jaggery (gur) gm	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Sugar gm	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

- G) The mixture was stirred continuously to ensure uniform distribution.
- H) The viscous mass was poured into pre-lubricated molds.
- I) It was allowed to cool and solidify at room temperature.

- J) The prepared candies were demolded, wrapped, and stored in airtight containers for further evaluation.
- K) Sugar and flavoring coating was applied to enhance taste and appearance.
- L) The coated candies were dried and stored in airtight containers for further evaluation.

Fig. 2 : Polyherbal Candy

2.2.4 Evaluation of Polyherbal Candy

The prepared polyherbal candies were evaluated for their organoleptic properties including colour, odour, taste, and appearance. Physicochemical parameters such as pH, consistency, and surface characteristics were also assessed to determine quality and stability. Texture properties like hardness and stickiness were observed manually.

Stability studies were conducted at regular intervals over a period of 60 days to monitor any changes in physical appearance, consistency, surface, odour, and pH. Based on these parameters, the formulations were analyzed for overall acceptability and stability.

Table 2: Comparative Evaluation of Formulations (F1-F9)

S. no	Parameter	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
1	Taste	Acceptable	Slightly better	Moderate	Good	Excellent	Good	Slightly strong	Strong	Very strong
2	Odour	Mild	Pleasant	Pleasant	Good	Best balanced	Good	strong	Strong	Very strong
3	Appearance	Good	Good	Good	Attractive	Very Attractive	Attractive	Slight Dull	Dull	Dull
4	Texture	Hard	Hard	Hard	Smooth	Smooth & non-stick	Slight sticky	sticky	Sticky	More sticky
5	Stability	Stable	Stable	Stable	Stable	Highly Stable	Stable	Slight change	Change	More change
6	Overall Acceptability	Good	Good	Good	Very Good	Best	Good	Moderate	Low	Poor

RESULT

The polyherbal anti-inflammatory functional candies were successfully formulated using *Boswelliaserrata*, *Cinnamomumverum*, and clove oil. All formulations (F1–F9) showed acceptable organoleptic properties with pleasant colour,

characteristic odour, and palatable taste. The candies exhibited good physicochemical characteristics, with pH values maintained in the range of approximately 5.4–5.8, indicating suitability for oral consumption. The consistency was initially hard and smooth, with gradual

changes to slight softness and stickiness observed during later stages of stability studies. Surface characteristics remained intact and smooth in the initial days, with minor stickiness observed over time.

Stability studies conducted over 60 days revealed no significant changes in colour, odour, or overall appearance, confirming good stability of the formulations. Among all, the optimized formulation demonstrated better stability, consistency, and overall acceptability. These findings indicate that the developed polyherbal candy is a stable, palatable, and promising formulation for supportive management of inflammation and joint health.

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated a polyherbal anti-inflammatory functional candy containing *Boswelliaserrata*, *Cinnamomumverum*, and *Syzygiumaromaticum*, known for their potent anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and analgesic activities due to bioactive compounds such as boswellic acids, cinnamaldehyde, and eugenol. Among the nine formulations (F1–F9), formulation F5 was identified as the optimized formulation based on comprehensive evaluation parameters. Formulation F5 exhibited excellent organoleptic properties, including pleasant taste, aroma, and smooth texture, ensuring high patient acceptability. It also showed desirable physicochemical characteristics such as uniform weight, proper hardness, stable pH, and good consistency. Stability studies confirmed that F5 remained stable without significant changes over time. Microbial limit tests indicated that the formulation complies with pharmacopeial standards and is safe for consumption. Additional evaluations such as friability, moisture content, and packaging confirmed its mechanical strength and protective stability. The synergistic action of

herbal ingredients enhances its anti-inflammatory potential. The candy dosage form provides improved palatability, ease of administration, and better patient compliance compared to conventional forms. Overall, the optimized formulation F5 represents a promising, innovative, and patient-friendly nutraceutical approach for inflammation management and joint support. However, further in vivo studies and clinical trials are required to confirm its therapeutic efficacy and long-term safety.

REFERENCES

1. Siddiqui M. Z. Puspita A, Kholifa M, and Rochmanita, N (2013) Pengaruh Konsentrasi Ekstrak Kulit kayumanis (*Cinnamomum burmanni*) dalam Menurunkan Pertumbuhan *Streptococcus mutans* secara In Vitro.
2. Fakultas Kedokteran Gigi UMS. Ammon H. P. T., H. P. T. (2006). Boswellic acids in chronic inflammatory diseases. *Planta Medica*, 72(12), 1100–1116.
3. B. Shan et al. (2005). Antioxidant properties of cinnamon extracts. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 53(20), 7749–7759.
4. Patel, K. K., et al. (2014). Formulation and evaluation of medicated lozenges. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, 4(5), 79–86.
5. Bajaj, S., Singla, D., & Sakhuja, N. (2012). Stability testing of pharmaceutical products. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*, 2(3), 129–138.
6. Bala, R., et al. (2012). Formulation and evaluation of herbal lozenges. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 4(Suppl 4), 282–285.
7. Jackson, E. B. (1995). *Sugar confectionery manufacture* (2nd ed.). Springer.
8. Schneiter, J. (2000). *Gout hater's cookbook: Recipes lower in purines and lower in fat*. Reachment Publications.

9. Hartel, R. W., & von Elbe, J. H. (2018). *Confectionery science and technology* (2nd ed.). Springer.
10. Fellows, P. J. (2009). *Food processing technology: Principles and practice*. Woodhead Publishing.
11. Bajaj, S., Singla, D., & Sakhuja, N. (2012). Stability testing of pharmaceutical products. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science*, 2(3), 129–138.
12. Buckwalter, J. A. (1995). Aging and degeneration of the human intervertebral disc. *Spine*, 20(11), 1307–1314.
13. Fakultas Kedokteran Gigi UMS. Ammon H. P. T., H. P. T. (2006). Boswellic acids in chronic inflammatory diseases. *Planta Medica*, 72(12), 1100–1116.
14. Just, J., et al. (2016). Extraction of eugenol from cloves: Alternative to steam distillation. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 93(1), 213–216.
15. S. K. Kulkarni et al. (2011). Pharmacological properties of *Boswelliaserrata*: A review. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 73(3), 255–261.
16. B. Shan et al. (2005). Antioxidant properties of cinnamon extracts. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 53(20), 7749–7759.
17. S. Siddiqui et al. (2011). Extraction and isolation of boswellic acids from *Boswelliaserrata*. *Journal of Natural Products*, 74(2), 200–205.

HOW TO CITE: Neha Chaudhari, Sandeep Mukati, Nivesh Pratap Singh Gurjar, Sudha Vengurlekar, Formulation and Evaluation of a Polyherbal Anti-Inflammatory Functional Candy Containing *Boswellia*, Cinnamon, and Clove Extract for Joint Support, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 5, 2849-2854, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20136268>

